

Magneto-Fluorescent Microrobots with Selective Detection Intelligence for High-energy Explosives and Antibiotics in Aqueous Environments

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NMR spectroscopic characterization of PAI

(a) 7-pyrrolidino-7,8,8-tricyanoquinodimethane (PTCNQ)

^1H NMR (60 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 7.68 (d, J = 9 Hz, 2H), δ 6.91 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H), δ 4.13 (M, 4H), δ 2.05 (M, 4H).

(b) 7-pyrrolidino-7-(1-(3-aminopropyl)imidazole)-8,8-dicyanoquinodimethane (PAI)

^1H NMR (60 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 8.32 (s, 1 H), δ 7.39 (s, 1 H), δ 6.90 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 2H), δ 6.70 (d, J = 5.4 Hz, 4H), δ 3.66 (t, J = 6.6 Hz, 2H), δ 3.05 (m, 6H), δ 1.75 (m, 6H).

Figure S1. ^1H NMR spectra of (a) PTCNQ and (b) PAI.

Single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis

Figure S2. Single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis of PAI. (a) Molecular structure, (b) Unit cell packing, (c) Supramolecular assembly view along the b axis. Intermolecular hydrogen bonds are shown as cyan lines. Carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen atoms are displayed as grey, blue, and red balls, respectively, and hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

Table S1. Basic crystallographic data of PAI

	PAI
Empirical formula	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₆ O
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>n</i>
<i>a</i> / Å	11.87797(6)
<i>b</i> / Å	9.32603(4)
<i>c</i> / Å	17.39728(10)
α / deg.	90
β / deg.	102.4585 (5)
γ / deg.	90
<i>V</i> / Å ³	1881.792(17)
<i>Z</i>	4
$\rho_{\text{calc.}}$ / g cm ⁻³	1.286
μ / mm ⁻¹	0.671
Temperature / K	120
λ / Å	1.54184
No. of reflections	3879
No. of parameters	250
Max., Min. transmission	0.874,0.904
GOF	1.058
R [for $I \geq 2\sigma_I$]	0.0344
wR ²	0.0859
Largest difference peak and hole / eÅ ⁻³	0.212/ -0.263
CCDC number	2404559

Mass spectroscopic analysis

Figure S3. MALDI MS intact mass spectroscopic analysis of PAI.

The mass spectrum was recorded on an UltrafleXtreme (Bruker Daltonics) Mass Spectrometer by reflection positive ion detection mode with α -cyano-4-hydroxycinnamic acid as a MALDI matrix.

Two peaks were observed at 347 and 534 Da.

The theoretical calculation for M (PAI, $C_{20}N_6H_{22}$) is 346.43 Da; found: 347.198 Da $[M+H]^+$. The second peak at 534 Da is attributed to adduct of the PAI molecule and MALDI matrix, α -cyano-4-hydroxycinnamic acid.

Aggregation induced emission

100 μl of 0.1 μM solution of PAI (in DMSO) was added to the series of solvent mixtures containing water and DMSO with increasing water fraction from 0 to 0.95, and their fluorescence emission spectra were recorded.

Figure S4. (a) Fluorescence emission spectra ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 350$ nm) and (b) corresponding fluorescence intensity variation of PAI in a solvent mixture containing DMSO and water with increasing water fraction from 0% to 95%.

Fabrication of PAI microrobots

Figure S5. A pictorial illustration of the fabrication of PAI microrobots.

PXRD and VSM analysis of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles

Figure S6. (a) PXRD pattern and (b) Magnetic hysteresis loop of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles used for the fabrication of microrobots in this study.

Synthesis of BAP and BC6

(a) 7,7-bis(2-(2-aminoethyl)pyridino)-8,8-dicyanoquinodimethane (BAP)

(b) 7,7-bis(cyclohexylamino)-8,8-dicyanoquinodimethane (BC6)

Figure S7. Synthesis of (a) BAP and (b) BC6.

NMR spectroscopic characterization of BAP and BC6

(a) 7,7-bis(2-(2-aminoethyl)pyridino)-8,8-dicyanoquinodimethane (BAP)

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (60 MHz, DMSO-d_6) δ 8.99 (bs, 2H), δ 8.47 (bs, 2H), δ 7.65 (bs, 2H), δ 7.24 (m, 4H), δ 6.68 (t, $J=7.8$, 4H), δ 3.58 (t, $J=6$ Hz, 4H), δ 3.00 (m, 4H).

(b) 7,7-bis(cyclohexylamino)-8,8-dicyanoquinodimethane (BC6)

$^1\text{H NMR}$ (60 MHz, DMSO-d_6) δ 8.95 (bs, 1H), δ 8.26 (bs, 1H), δ 7.10 (d, 2H), δ 6.75 (d, 2H), δ 3.66 (m, 1H), δ 2.99 (m, 1H), 1.32 (m, 20H)

Figure S8. $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra of (a) BAP and (b) BC6.

Detection of picric acid

Figure S9. (a) Electronic absorption and (b) fluorescence emission spectra of PAI microrobots with increasing concentration of picric acid (PA).

Molecular structure of nitroaromatic explosives

Caution! The nitroaromatic compounds used in this study (TNT and PA) are highly dangerous explosives. They should be handled very carefully and also in very small quantities.

Figure S10. Molecular structure of nitro compounds used in this study.

Plausible reaction mechanism between PAI and picric acid

Figure S11. Plausible reaction mechanism between PAI and picric acid (PA).

FTIR spectra of BC6 with picric acid and tetracycline

Figure S12. FTIR spectra of bare BC6, BC6 treated with picric acid and tetracycline, bare picric acid (PA), and bare tetracycline (TC).

Limit of detection for picric acid

Figure S13. (a) Electronic absorption and (b) fluorescence emission spectra of PAI molecules with increasing concentration of picric acid (PA), (c) Linear plot of fluorescence emission intensity versus concentration of picric acid (PA).

LOD calculation:

$$\text{Slope (k)} = 4344 \times 10^6 \text{ intensity/M}$$

$$\text{Standard deviation } (\sigma) = 282 \text{ intensity (n=6)}$$

$$\text{Limit of detection} = 3.3 \sigma/k$$

$$= 3.3 \times (282 / 4344 \times 10^6) \text{ M}$$

$$\text{LOD} = 0.214 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$$

$$= 214 \text{ nM}$$

Locomotion of microrobots towards dinitrotoluene (DNT)

Figure S14. Time lapse locomotion images of microrobots toward the target area filled with dinitrotoluene (DNT) in a fluidic channel (scale bars: 1 cm).

Comparison of detection performance of PAI microrobots with other fluorescent sensing probes to picric acid

Table S2. Comparison of detection performance of various fluorescent probes including MOFs, COFs, small organic molecules, CDs, and polymer materials to picric acid (PA)

Sr. No.	Probes	microrobots	LOD (M)	Solvent system	Ref.
1	Histidine	No	2.71×10^{-6}	Aqueous	S1
2	Anthracene-bridged poly(<i>N</i> -vinyl pyrrolidone)	No	6×10^{-9}	Aqueous	S2
3	Amine-functionalized α -cyanostilbene derivatives	No	2.85×10^{-7}	Aqueous	S3
4	Quinoline based sensor	No	9.33×10^{-6}	Aqueous	S4
5	Ni-MOF	No	0.29×10^{-6}	Aqueous	S5
6	Porous organic polymer	No	8×10^{-6}	Aqueous	S6
7	Terbium based metal organic framework	No	1.3×10^{-5}	Aqueous	S7
8	Carbon dots-embedded ZIF-8 nanocomposite	No	2.58×10^{-5}	Aqueous	S8
9	Fe ₂ O ₃ -CdSe nanocomposite	No	2.2×10^{-6}	Aqueous	S9
10	NP-CQD	No	23×10^{-6}	Aqueous	S10
11	Cd(II) coordination polymer	No	8.36×10^{-6}	Aqueous	S11
12	Aniline-based covalent organic frameworks	No	1.06×10^{-9}	Aqueous	S12
13	Covalent Organic Cage	No	2.7×10^{-9}	Aqueous	S13
14	Nitrogen-Doped Carbon Dots	No	33×10^{-9}	Aqueous	S14
15	PAI	Yes	214×10^{-9}	Aqueous	This work

Detection of Tetracycline

Figure S15. (a) Electronic absorption, and (b) fluorescence emission spectra of PAI microrobots with increasing concentration of Tetracycline (TC).

Plausible reaction mechanism between PAI and tetracycline

Figure S16. Plausible reaction mechanism between PAI molecule and tetracycline hydrochloride (TC).

Effect of tetracycline on morphology and fluorescence of PAI microrobots

(a)

(b)

Figure S17. (a) FESEM (scale bars: 10 μm) and (b) fluorescence microscopic images (scale bars: 50 μm) of PAI microrobots upon exposure to increasing concentration of tetracycline (TC).

Limit of detection for Tetracycline

Figure S18. (a) Electronic absorption and (b) fluorescence emission spectra of PAI molecules with increasing concentration of tetracycline (TC). (c) Linear plot of fluorescence emission intensity versus concentration of tetracycline.

LOD calculation:

$$\text{Slope (k)} = 2657 \times 10^6 \text{ intensity/M}$$

$$\text{Standard deviation } (\sigma) = 282 \text{ intensity (n=6)}$$

$$\text{Limit of detection} = 3.3 \sigma/k$$

$$= 3.3 \times (282 / 2657 \times 10^6) \text{ M}$$

$$\text{LOD} = 0.3502 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$$

$$= 350 \text{ nM}$$

Comparison of detection performance of PAI microrobots with other fluorescent sensing probes to tetracycline

Table S3. Comparison of detection performance of various fluorescent probes including MOFs, DNA aptamer, small organic molecules, and CDs to tetracycline (TC).

Sr. No.	Probes	microrobots	LOD (M)	Solvent system	Ref.
1	Copper doped carbon dots	No	0.16×10^{-6}	Water	S15
2	Self-assembled copper nanoclusters	No	40×10^{-9}	Water, human urine and milk samples	S16
3	Lanthanide coordination polymer nanoparticles	No	3.4×10^{-9}	Water, honey, paper strip	S17
4	4-formyl-3-hydroxybenzoic acid	No	60×10^{-9}	Water, milk and honey samples	S18
5	Hydrogel based on wood-derived cellulose nanocrystals (WCNs) and carbon dots (CDs)	No	0.11×10^{-6}	Aqueous	S19
6	Al-MOF@Mo	No	0.56×10^{-9}	Water, Food samples	S20
7	LMOF-241	No	46 ppb	Aqueous	S21
8	Zeolitic imidazolate framework-8 (ZIF-8)	No	5.99×10^{-6}	water and food samples	S22
9	Glutamic acid-capped iron oxide quantum dots	No	7.69×10^{-9}	Urine	S23
10	Tris-Zn ²⁺	No	$\sim 7.0 \times 10^{-9}$	Water & chicken broth sample	S24
11	ZIF-8	No	14.7×10^{-9}	Aqueous	S25
12	DNA aptamer for oxytetracycline	No	25×10^{-9}	Aqueous	S26
13	UiO-66-NH ₂	No	0.449×10^{-6}	Aqueous, milk	S27
14	PAI	Yes	350×10^{-9}	Aqueous	This work

Effect of pH on the detection performance of PAI microrobots to picric acid and tetracycline

Figure S19. Fluorescence intensity changes of PAI microrobots with (a) picric acid (PA) and (b) tetracycline (TC) in the BR buffer solutions (pH 2-11).

Effect of metal ionic species on the detection performance of PAI microrobots to picric acid

Figure S20. Fluorescence intensity changes of PAI microrobots with picric acid (PA) in various metal ionic species.

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